

CULTUROLOGY

NATIONAL GAMES AMONG KYRGYZ AND AMERICAN TRIBAL PEOPLE

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Abstract

Gaming has deep historical roots among the Kyrgyz people and tribal people in the Americas. It is connected to rituals of play and storytelling that link the peoples to their communal origins and destiny. Traditional games played by American Indians had cultural or religious significance, and gaming was often a sacred act connected to myth, legend, and ritual. Games were also used for entertainment and as a teaching tool (Fairebaugh, Tippeconnic, 2019, p.76).

For the Kyrgyz people, games have been played since ancient times and were a moment of truce during warring times between tribes. There were valuable prizes for winners of the games, with the most valuable being horses and other domestic animals. The American Indians learned about horses only after the Europeans entered their territories in the mid-14th century. Games served as a way for American tribal people to improve their position within their own tribe and often served to redistribute wealth among tribal members. This was widely misunderstood by non-Indians during the early years of the country, leading to misrepresentations of American Indians, especially males who gambled, as lazy and wasteful. This stereotype was reinforced by scholars such as Francis Parkman and Henry Morgan, who viewed Native gambling only in European-American terms and never attempted to understand the tribal perspective. The disparate accumulation of wealth was not encouraged by traditional Indian societies, which stressed the notions of balance and strong interrelationships (Paul Pasquaretta, *Gambling and Survival in Native North America*, Tucson: The University of Arizona Press, 2003), 119–20..

Keywords: Games, customs, traditions, tribal people.

Many writers and poets compare our lives to a game, where each player has a role. The ability to play and give free rein to one's imagination, without worrying about immediate results, is evident in children's amusements and adult entertainment, and it is a fundamental aspect of humanity. Scholars have shown that the game is closely associated with an individual's desire to explore the unknown and satisfy their curiosity, and it encourages people and all higher animals to explore the world around us. Emphasizing a casual game in a particular culture gives us an opportunity to assess its main features.

The game is a phenomenon inherent in all living nature, not just in humans. Studies show that all higher animals use play as a way of communicating, spending time, and learning. In humans, the game has reached the peak of its development. Humans play throughout their lives. It is important to highlight that even in the simplest forms, the game goes beyond biological or physical activity. The game is a meaningful function with many facets of meaning. In any scientific approach, it is universally accepted that the game serves a necessary and useful function. In childhood, the game is a way of learning to communicate, developing certain skills, and so on. In adulthood, many activities are also associated with the gaming component. Additionally, people use games to communicate, relax, and structure their leisure time.

The game can serve as a harmless outlet for pent-up energy and the need for variety in daily activities. It can provide a sense of satisfaction, allowing individuals to fulfill unrealistic desires and maintain a sense of personal stability. Many researchers seek to understand the

essence of games and why players become so engrossed, often losing themselves in the experience. The intensity of gaming cannot be fully explained by biological factors alone. Yet, it is this very intensity that captures the essence of gaming, its fundamental quality. Nature has bestowed upon us the gift of games, with their stress, joy, humor, and amusement.

Games have been a part of human existence since the beginning of time. They accompany us throughout our lives, and some games have even evolved into customs and traditions. Games vary from one group of people to another. In this article, I will explore two distinct groups: the Kyrgyz and Native Americans. Despite their geographical separation, they both belong to tribal cultures.

“In recent decades Western historians and anthropologists have come closer together in common endeavors to reexamine both Western and Third World society and history. A welcome feature of this trend has been the willingness of each kind of specialist to learn from the other in studying the tribal peoples of the so called Fourth World. In most cases a lack of documentation gives anthropologist precedence, but various tribal peoples have participated in the economics and politics of states and empires long enough and actively enough to have left a considerable mark in the archives, even producing their own chronicles” (Khoury, Kostiner 1990, p. 45)

Most of the scholars were naming tribal people as “primitive society” outlining them as a culturally and linguistically primitive too. But it was quite an inappropriate for the cultural groups as Arabs, Turks, Persians, Berbers, Pashtuns and etc. which can hardly be termed either tribes or primitive societies, if only on grounds

of scale, complexity, and lack of unity (Khoury, Kostiner 1990, p. 53)

In this article, I am eager to explore the traditional games of the Kyrgyz people and the games of American Indian tribes. I have a keen interest in the language, culture, and customs of American Indians, and I have previously published several articles on the topics connected with culture and languages, which have some similarities. Here, I am excited to delve into the unique and traditional games of both of these cultures.

The Kyrgyz games

The paper I am presenting today focuses on the games that are an integral part of tribal culture. While the culture of Kyrgyz and Amerindian tribal communities has been extensively studied and discussed, the games that are central to their way of life have not received as much attention. All games are national values and people try to keep them and teach their children to play into those games.

Despite living in close proximity to other cultures, the Kyrgyz people have maintained their unique way of life and traditional forms of entertainment over the centuries. This was evident during the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd World Nomad Games held in Kyrgyzstan in 2014, 2016, and 2018. These games not only showcased traditional nomadic competitions but also highlighted the cultural significance of the Kyrgyz people to the world. One can get a glimpse of the national games by observing children playing with sheep knuckle bones or lacrosse balls. These games are a testament to the rich cultural heritage and unique way of life of tribal communities.

The Kyrgyz people have a tradition of playing games during big festivals, and winning a prize is considered a great honor. The most popular games for Kyrgyz children involve riding a horse or creating a horse using various materials such as wood or stone. Parents would provide their children with toys that would help them learn skills they could use as adults. For girls, mothers and grandmothers would make dolls dressed in traditional Kyrgyz clothing, and the girls would sew the clothes themselves to prepare for their future roles as wives and mothers. Through these games, Kyrgyz children were taught skills that would prepare them for adulthood. Games were a significant part of Kyrgyz social life and played a role in the upbringing of children. Because the Kyrgyz people were nomadic, many of the games were related to horses and riding.

The game from the other side was a business for adults, such as cock-fighting, which was a real and very popular game among settled Kyrgyz tribes. It usually took place at big markets and people would place bets. On the other hand, games involving horses were mostly for the youth, such as racing, and also involved big betting during big festivals or wakes dedicated to well-known or famous people (e.g. Kokotaidin Ashi). When discussing Kyrgyz people, it is important to highlight their national pride, and after customs and traditions, Kyrgyz national games and sports come to mind. Not long ago, these games were included in the list of Nomadic Olympic games, such as Kok bory, Kiz Kyymai, Odarysh, and Kyrgyz chess (Togyz kymalak or Togyz korgool), among many others.

The most well-known game is *At Chabysh*, also known as horse racing. It is an ancient game, and the horse for this race must be prepared and trained in a

special way so that it can easily run and win the game. The horse's age should not be less than 3 years old. The race distance was originally 53 miles (100 km), but now it ranges from 4-50 km. Racers should not be younger than 13 years old.

Another type of racing is *Jorgo-salysh*, which is one of the most beautiful types of racing. In this race, the horse moves two legs together in a balanced way, which is called "allure" in modern racing. This is a special art of training the horse and is considered the top art of racing.

One of the main national games of the Kyrgyz people is the team game "**Kök-boru**" (The grey wolf), where teams of 12 members play on the field from both sides.

The territory for this game is usually chosen by both sides together, and it is typically around 500 meters long and 250-300 meters in depth. In the middle, there is a "tai kazan," a national Asian kettle for boiling the meat of a young horse. The rules are similar to modern football, and the goal is to put the body of a goat weighing around 30-40 kilograms into the tai kazan as a goal within a set time. The players must keep the body of the goat with one hand and control the horse with the other hand. The goal in this game is around 10 meters. At the beginning of the game, the team captains fight for the body of the goat, and the team that wins keeps the body and can start to attack the tai kazan to score a goal.

Another fascinating game is *Oodarysh*, also known as wrestling on the back of a horse, which only the strongest players of the team could participate in. Similar to *Oodarysh* is *Küresh*, where the riders remove their clothes and sit on a horse wearing only pants and leather belts. The main objective of this game is for the fighters to take the opponent off the horse by grabbing their belt.

The tradition of racing to pick up a coin from the ground, commonly seen in circuses, has its roots in nomadic games. In *Tyin Enmei*, the horse and the rider must work together as a team to pick up the coin while racing at high speed. The winner is the one who collects the most coins.

Kiz Kyymai is another race that includes girls, with the girls racing ahead and the boys trying to catch them. If a boy catches a girl, he gets to kiss her, but if he fails, the girl gets to publicly whip him.

Among the nomadic people, the Kyrgyz people have *Kiz jarysh*, a race for girls and newly married women. The married and unmarried girls can be distinguished by the type of hats they wear, with unmarried girls wearing one type of hat and married women wearing a kerchief on their heads.

Another type of Kyrgyz national sport is *Jaa atmai* - archery, which involves riding on horseback. This is a very exciting game that young men and women can participate in. It is considered a shame if a participant misses the target, which is a needle attached to a silver plate.

One of the most beautiful and attractive types of Kyrgyz national sport is *Angchylık* hunting with eagles or falcons. Kyrgyz hunters still use eagles and falcons for hunting. There are many legends about this type of hunting, with stories of eagles easily capturing hares and deer. Hunters spend several years training their eagles and falcons before they are ready for real hunting. Another important helper in this type of

hunting is the Kyrgyz hound, a very smart dog and a great friend to the hunter. I have mentioned games that are mostly connected with horses.

Tolstoy once wrote: "If we always judged from reality, games would be nonsense. But if games were nonsense, what else would there be left to do" (Cited in Opie and Opie 1969: 338). Tolstoy, in justifying play, suggests several dimensions that are central to the understanding of shared fantasy: reality/fantasy, work/games, (play), and sense/nonsense. Often, fantasy, play, and nonsense have been depicted as opposed to the important activities of human life - working and knowing the real world. These dichotomies have influenced even those who profess not to accept their implications" (Alan, 1983).

The American Indians and their games

Game playing is a pastime enjoyed by most people, and Native Americans are no exception. The origins of many games were with the tribal gods, and because of this, games were played ceremonially to bring rain, ensure good harvests, cure illness, expel evil spirits, or give pleasure to the gods by demonstrating physical fitness. Though games are usually played for fun and pleasure, Native American games also played a role in the education of children by helping them develop skills necessary to be successful adults. In general, boys and girls played separately, though they often might play the same games with variations in the rules. Certain ceremonial games were forbidden to women, particularly those games which might disrupt the protective powers of hunting and warfare spirits. In addition to games similar to boys' games, girls played "house," sometimes with miniature tipis or igloos. They also had dolls made from various materials such as wood, grasses, corn husks, animal skin, or bone. Doll play helped girls learn the skills of childcare (Lavine, Sigmund, 1974)

Native Americans highly honored skilled athletes just as they honored brave warriors. Many games played by men and boys served to train them in skills needed for warfare and/or hunting. These games tested a boy's skill, dexterity, agility, strength, and stamina.

The Cherokee Indians refer to stickball games as "the little brother of war." Children played most of the same games as adults. In addition, they enjoyed races, tug-of-war, hide and seek, and blind man's bluff types of games. Native American games fall into two general categories: games of chance, the outcome of which depends on luck, and games of skill. Games of chance are played with sticks, dice, or involved guessing. Skill games require physical and/or mental abilities. In the past, many games were played with balls made of animal skin stuffed with grass or hair, or inflated animal bladders (Internet sources). Native American game Kit, Bull Roarer, Buzz Toy, Ring and Pin, Running Game, Laughing Game, Game of Silence, Bean Game Etc. (Underwood, Thomas Bryan, 1979)

Native American Game Kit

This kit includes an assortment of games of both skill and chance, plus directions for variations of running games. There are games suitable for both indoors and outside play, as well as a variety of group sizes. Equipment for several players or two teams are included in the kit. Also, there are directions for simple and inexpensive versions of the games. These could be made at home or as part of a classroom study. We suggest that when large numbers of children are using the

kit, several stations be set up and the group divided so everyone would be playing different games but at the same time. By rotating groups, the children could have an opportunity to learn and play most or all of the games. Since a variety of games are in the kit, teachers are encouraged to select the games that best suit their needs.

Lacrosse. The best known of Indian games is lacrosse. It was most common among the tribes of the Atlantic seaboard and around the Great Lakes, but it was also played in the South, on the plains, in California, and in the Pacific Northwest. It was played with a ball made either of wood or of buckskin, which was caught with curved rackets with a net on one end. The goal was usually marked with two poles although in some areas only one was used. In 1860 J. G. Kohl, a white traveler in Wisconsin, examined some lacrosse equipment. He admired the fine carving of crosses, circles, and stars on the white willow ball and praised lacrosse as "the finest and grandest" sport of the Indians. Although he was unable to see a game, he claimed that the Indians "often play village against village or tribe against tribe. Hundreds of players assemble, and the wares and goods offered as prizes often reach a value of a thousand dollars and more." (Underwood, Thomas Bryan, 1979)

Shinny. A kind of field hockey known as shinny was among the most popular Native American games. **Shinny**, generally believed to be a precursor to **ice hockey** It was usually played by women, but sometimes, especially on the plains, might also be played by men. Among the Sauk, Foxes, and Assiniboine Indians, men and women played the game together, and among the Crows, teams of men played against teams of women. Native Americans in the East, on the plains, in the Southwest, and on the Pacific Coast played shinny. It was played with a ball or bag, often made of buckskin, which was hit with sticks curved at one end. The ball and sticks might be decorated with paint or beads. The length of the field varied from two hundred yards (among the Miwok Indians) to a mile or more (among the Navajos). The object of the game was to hit the ball through the opponent's goal. The ball could be kicked or hit with the stick but not touched with the hands (<https://nativeamericans.mrdonn.org/games.html>)

Snow-Snake. In regions of the West cold enough to have snow and ice in the winter, snow-snake was played. Its rules varied even more than those of lacrosse or shinny, but in general the game involved sliding darts or poles along snow or ice as far as possible. The projectile could be only a few inches long or might be a javelin up to ten feet long. The game was usually, but not always, played by men. Among the Crees, who played a variant of the game in which the dart had to pass through barriers of snow, only men played the game. Among the Arapahos, on the other hand, snow-snake might be played by adults or children but was most commonly played by girls (<https://nativeamericans.mrdonn.org/games.html>).

Hoop and Pole. Hoop and pole was another widespread game with varying rules. In general a hoop was rolled along the ground while men tried to knock it over with spears or arrows. The hoop was usually relatively small, from three inches to a foot in diameter. The hoop might be open, but often the players stretched cords or a net across it. The hoop itself was often of wood but might be made of corn husks, stone, or iron. It was sometimes decorated with paint or beads. The score

was determined by the way the hoop fell when hit by the pole. The game was most frequently played by two men although in some cases more participated.

Iditarod and Alaska Native Games

For Alaska Natives, the tradition of ancestral games is as strong as ever. Most famous is the Iditarod dog sled race, a highly competitive endurance sport that promotes survival skills in a challenging Arctic environment. Alaska Native John Baker of Kotzebue won the 2011 Iditarod in record-breaking time. At annual events such as Alaska Native Youth Games and the World Eskimo-Indian Olympics, children and adults test their strength, endurance, and agility in traditional contests such as the high kick, in which competitors kick balls suspended at head level or higher. As of 2011, the world record was 7' 10" for men, and 6' 1" for women. Other more conventional sports, such as basketball and cribbage, are also important to Native communities, young and old, especially during the long winters

(<https://nativeamericans.mrdonn.org/games.html>).

Native Hawaiian Sports: At Sea and on Land

Hawai'i is justly famous for its water sports of canoeing, surfboarding, and swimming. Canoe and paddling clubs attract large numbers of members of all ages. Events range from outrigger canoe races on weekends to sea-going voyages in traditional double-hulled canoes such as the Hōkūle'a. The iconic Hawaiian sport of surfboarding was a tradition that was nearly lost by the turn of the 20th century. It was revived by the Native Hawaiian sportsman Duke Kahanamoku, who in three successive Olympics also won medals in swimming. Kahanamoku is revered in Hawai'i, with his statue prominently located on Waikiki Beach, Honolulu. (<https://media.gohawaii.com/statewide/press-room/story-ideas/modern-ways-experience-traditional-hawaiian-sports>)

The story of the American Indians is, without a doubt, one of survival. It is estimated that in AD 1500, 100 million indigenous people lived in prosperous nations within the current boundaries of the United States. That population would nose-dive, however, to a scant 250,000 by 1900 as a result of germ warfare, military actions, and genocidal policies. As U.S. Gen. William T. Sherman would complain in the mid-1800s, if not for civilian interference, his army would have gotten rid of all American Indians.⁶ The poverty and other substandard economic situations of most Indian tribes in the past are undisputed. Native Americans traditionally have been among the poorest of the poor.⁷ One of the main obstacles to economic success for these tribes has been the location of their lands. Many tribal reservations, *rancherias*, pueblos, and other landholdings are in rural or isolated locations. Remoteness was often preferable from a cultural-preservation standpoint, but it worked against later efforts to develop economies on the reservations (Firebaughand, Tippeconnic Spring 2010 pp 75-86).

Access to markets is one of the most important components of economy building, and much tribal land is simply too isolated to attract customers. Examples of this in Indian gaming can be seen where location is the key factor in a gaming facility's success (Froelich, Schaller, and Klaczek, 2005., p19–25).

The tribal casinos that are most successful are located close to urban markets. Location can be particu-

larly favorable to Indian casinos in the case of an economic downturn; when airplane fares and other costs of transportation are high, some gaming customers prefer to drive to a relatively close Indian casino instead of to large gaming establishments that are farther away.

In the twenty-first century, American Indian gaming is big business, but it has always been around. American Indian nations have always played games, and this gaming was and is an important custom. Traditionally, it served to preserve culture and ceremonies, redistribute wealth, and teach traditional values to community members and children. Skill and luck came together to level the playing field upon which all lived their lives. Today games of skill and luck, such as the hand games at Northwest Coast Tribal Stommash, are huge attractions and can go on, around the clock, for days at a time. While traditional forms of games continue throughout Indian Country, casino-type gambling has turned into a major modern industry for Indian nations. Since 1832 the U.S. Supreme Court has upheld the right of Native American tribes to self-rule, allowing them to control everything from fishing, hunting, and mineral rights to the establishment of gaming casinos. In the 1960s no states ran lotteries, and only one, Nevada, allowed casinos. Beginning in the late 1970s, however, a number of Indian tribes established bingo operations in order to raise revenues to fund tribal governments. In 1987, in *California v. Cabazon Band of Mission Indians*, the U.S. Supreme Court upheld one of the most significant turning points for tribal governments: the legal right of Native American tribes to offer gaming on reservation lands, free of state interference. Essentially, the band argued that its status as a sovereign government prevented state interference in its affairs (Froelich, Schaller, and Klaczek, 2005., p34).

The publication of Steward Culin's study, *Games of the North American Indians*, changed academic attitudes about the role of gaming in the social and spiritual lives of American Indians. This comprehensive account of gaming was a collaborative effort between Frank Cushing, an ethnologist, and Steward Culin, curator of the Columbian Exposition in Chicago. The study, which took fourteen years to complete, was published in 1907. Culin's investigation showed widespread gaming among 229 tribes in North America and Mexico. More than thirty-six different kinds of games were used throughout the Western Hemisphere and predated Europeans. The games were classified as those of chance or dexterity; games of chance used dice-like pieces, with players guessing on the outcome of a throw, while games of dexterity included archery, sliding, javelins or darts, shooting a netted or stone wheel or ring, ball games, and racing. Some tribes combined activities; for example, the Iroquois played a combination of six principal games divided into athletic contests and games of chance. The study showed nearly every tribe played several versions of games, but not all games were played or could be gambled upon. Games were played by adults, most restricted to one gender and occurring at fixed times or during certain festivals and religious rites frequently associated with spiritual beliefs and practices. During the games, wagering possessions was not uncommon for American Indians (Culin S., 1992)

Casino growth on a national level has occurred most significantly in Native American communities. One of the main reasons for this is, as mentioned ear-

lier, that tribal communities have the ability to self-govern without the influence of state governments. As of 2006, because of their ability to self-govern, gaming tribes operated in twenty-eight states: Alaska, Arizona, California, Colorado, Connecticut, Florida, Idaho, Iowa, Kansas, Louisiana, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi, Missouri, Montana, Nebraska, Nevada, New Mexico, New York, North Carolina, North Dakota, Oklahoma, Oregon, South Dakota, Texas, Washington, Wisconsin, and Wyoming. Four of these states, California, Connecticut, Florida, and New York, experienced major growth in tribal gaming (Froelich, Schaller, and Klaczek, 2005., p34).

As of 2008 233 Indian tribes, including two Alaska Native villages, operated 411 casinos, bingo halls, and pull-tab operations spread through-out the same 28 states listed above, creating more than 636,000 jobs: 284,000 direct Indian gaming, 102,000 indirect Indian gaming, and 208,000 Indian gaming and government projects.²³ In addition, Indian gaming revenues, as shown in figure 1, topped \$26.7 billion. This compares very favorably to revenues of \$7.4 billion twelve years earlier (National Indian Gaming Commission, June 2009)

Tribal gaming is different from other forms of gaming. It is conducted by Native American governments as a way to carry out their natural self-governing rights as independent nations. As such, there are three formal classes of gaming (Schaap2010), pp. 365-389)

Class I gaming includes social games for prizes of minimal value and traditional forms of tribal gaming as a part of or in connection with tribal ceremonies or celebrations (e.g., contests and games of skill). Because no money is exchanged here, Class I gaming is regulated solely by the tribes.

Class II gaming includes bingo, other games similar to bingo (e.g., pull-tabs, lotto, punch boards, tip jars, instant bingo) if conducted at the same location, and certain non-house-banked card games allowed in a state (i.e., poker). (Nonbanking refers to poker and other card games in which players bet against each other rather than against the house.) The use of technological aids in conducting such games is permitted. Subject to certain conditions set forth in IGRA and some oversight by the National Indian Gaming Commission, Class II gaming is also regulated by tribes

Class III gaming includes all other types of gaming not considered to be Class I or Class II, including slot machines, other video and electronic games of chance, craps, roulette, pari-mutuel wagering, and house-banked card games like blackjack. Class III gaming is governed by tribal-state compacts (Schaap2010), pp. 365-389).

Native games as Kyrgyz so American Indian's are more than just games, they build body and spirit through exercise and are played by all age groups—children, youth, and adults. Many games have roots in

ancestral tests of strength and sport that reinforced group cooperation and sharpened survival skills in often hostile environments. For warriors, the games helped maintain their readiness and combat skills between times of war. Today, games are as important as ever. The gradual shift to a more sedentary lifestyle has highlighted the need to reawaken interest in physical activity, especially among Native youth. Promoting games and sports is an important part of improving the health and well-being of Native populations (Lavine, Sigmund,1974).

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that this article represents the first attempt to compare Kyrgyz games with the games of Native American Indian tribal people. The games of each group provide opportunities to acquire knowledge and skills, both physical and mental, and were essential not only for children but also for adults.

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